

RCPL-32 and RCPL-3-6: two promising rice lines for the mid-hills of Sikkim, India

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Rice is the second most important crop in Sikkim, India covering about 19,000 ha. Yields average 1.3 t ha⁻¹. In Sikkim, rice is cultivated on terraces using gravity flow water. Commonly grown local cultivars (Attey, Chirkey, Krishnabhog, Tapre, Kalonunia, Tulasi, Champasare, and Bhuinphool) are late-maturing, tall, and low-tillering. Their yields are poor but they have good quality attributes. Suitable substitutes for these cultivars must be semi-tall, medium-maturing, nonlodging, have low photoperiod sensitivity, high yield potential, and good quality. After 4 yr of evaluation, lines RCPL-3-2 and RCPL-3-6 outyielded all other lines and checks (Table 1).

RCPL-3-2, a selection from cross Moirangphou/Jaya, is semidwarf (98-105 cm), while RCPL-3-6, a selection from cross CH-988/IR24, is also semidwarf but slightly taller. RCPL-3-2 is nonglutinous, whereas RCPL-3-6 is a semiglutinous rice. Both are medium in maturity and resistant

Toag92: a shortduration rice cultivar for Turkey

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Toag92, a rice variety derived from the cross Nucleoryza/Labela, was released in 1992. The main aim of the breeding program was to create a variety that does well in the second cropping season in the Aegean and Mediterranean regions of Turkey. Toag92, however, also has high yields in northern Turkey, where it did particularly well when sown late and in areas where existing varieties cannot be grown because of their long vegetative

Table 1. Grain yield (t ha⁻¹) of promising lines and checks over years and locations in Sikkim, India.

Location	Year	RCPL-3-2	RCPL-3-6	DR-92	Attey
Tadong	1990	5.0	4.3	3.8	2.0
Tadong	1991	5.0	4.5	2.9	1.2
Tadong	1992	4.1	4.6	2.5	1.3
Tadong	1993	4.3	4.4	3.0	1.8
Tadong	1994	4.2	4.4	3.6	1.4
Pakyong	1992	4.0	4.6	3.3	1.9
Pakyong	1993	3.9	3.5	2.6	2.2
Dharmdin	1992	6.0	5.5	3.8	2.2
Nazitam	1992	4.9	4.6	3.5	2.1
Nazitam	1993	4.9	4.6	3.2	2.0

Table 2. Important characteristics of RCPL-3-2 and RCPL-3-6.

Characteristic	RCPL-3-2	RCPL-3-6
Plant height (cm)	98-105	110-115
Days to flowering	60-70	67-72
Days to maturity	115-120	120-125
Ear-bearing tillers (no.)	9-15	8-14
Panicle length (cm)	20-23	25-27
Flag leaf	Erect	Erect
Awn type	Awnless	Awnless
Husk grain color	Straw	Straw
Kernel color	Dull	Dull
1,000-grain weight (g)	25.4	23.5
Grain length (cm)	0.83	0.84
Grain width (cm)	0.30	0.28
L-B ratio	2.77	2.94
Endosperm type	Nonglutinous	Semiglutinous
Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	4.5-5.0	4.2-4.6
Reaction to leaf blast (0-9 scale)	0-2	0-2
Reaction to neck blast (%)	0-1	0-1

to lodging, leaf and neck blast. Distinguishing traits for both include panicle length, 1,000-grain weight, L-B ratio, panicle-bearing tillers, and endosperm type (Table 2).

RCPL-3-2 and RCPL-3-6 are suitable for early sowing, and will enable farmers to adopt more profitable rice-based cropping systems such as rice-mustard/pea/barley, that promise to increase cropping intensity under rainfed conditions. ■

Table 1. Comparison of some agronomic characters of Toag92 and commercial varieties. Bornova, Turkey (3-yr av).

Variety	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Height (cm)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Yield (kg d ⁻¹)	Duration (d)	Sterility (%)	Leaf blast ^a
Toag 92	5.3	64	33	5.95	89	16	0
Baldo	4.1	92	38	3.66	112	24	-
Ribe	4.5	99	33	4.24	106	30	8
Krasnodorsky 424	4.4	101	31	4.40	100	24	4

^aScored using the *Standard evaluation system* (SES) 0-9 scale where 0 = highly resistant and 9 = highly susceptible.

durations. Toag92 matures 2 wk earlier than Ribe.

Its low sterility under Mediterranean conditions makes it promising for the southeastern Anatolia region, where August temperatures are quite high.

Toag92 is of medium height (88 cm), 30 cm shorter than Ribe, and is resistant to lodging. The yield d⁻¹ of Toag92 is almost 50% more than that of other improved cultivars. Toag92 is also resistant to leaf blast (Table 1).